

MECHANICAL AND THERMAL BEHAVIOR CHARACTERIZATION OF

COMPOSITE MATERIALS FOR COMMUNICATIONS SPACECRAFT

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Abstract

In communications satellites and planetary probes, the low thermal expansion coefficients of graphite and polyaramid-epoxies are used to great advantage in applications requiring both high specific stiffness and low thermal expansion. These applications include high-gain reflectors, antenna feeds, waveguides, filters, etc. Such structures require that the mechanical and thermal properties of advanced composites be characterized since even small local displacements due to viscoelastic stress relaxation or micro-cracking can result in frequency drift and signal attenuation large enough to cause failure of the communications system.

Two areas of practical importance were investigated: the effect of long-term thermal cycling on metallized graphite-epoxy, and the stability of the coefficient of thermal expansion. An elastoplastic analysis was conducted to define the stress-strain state of the copper plating during thermal cycling. The results of the analysis were compared with an experimental study of the failure modes resulting from thermal cycling. Using scanning electron microscopy, the effect of thermal cycling on a variety of metallized graphite-epoxy substrates was determined. The predominant failure mode appears to be one in which microcracks generated in the substrate propagate into and cause failure of the plating. The coefficient of thermal expansion of graphite-epoxy tubular specimens was found to vary significantly in the first few thermal cycles. These changes, which may cause the coefficient of thermal expansion to either increase or decrease with cycling, were attributed to the growth of interlaminar macrodefects.

Advanced composites are used extensively in spacecraft applications because of their high specific stiffness and strength. In communications satellites and planetary probes, the low thermal expansion coefficients of graphite and polyaramid-epoxies are used to great advantage in microwave applications which require both high specific stiffness and low coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE). Such applications currently include high-gain reflectors, antenna feed support structures, waveguides and microwave filters.

At Ford Aerospace and Communications Corporation - Western Development Laboratories (FACC-WDL), an example of an eminently successful application was the 1.5 m high-gain reflector built for the Viking orbiter (1). Graphite-epoxy face-skins were used with a sandwiched machined aluminum honeycomb core to provide an extremely accurate parabolic dish structure weighing less than 5 kg. Similar construction was employed in the 3.7 m Voyager high-gain reflector (currently on its way to Jupiter and Saturn), which is probably the largest non-deployable spacecraft reflector built. This reflector also features a unique metallized polyaramid-epoxy frequency selective subreflector in which the dielectric properties and matched CTE of the polyaramid-epoxy are integrated with the main graphite-epoxy structure to form a dimensionally stable and accurate reflector assembly. Another example of advanced composites application to communications systems is the Japanese Communications Satellite (CS) which was recently launched into geosynchronous orbit (2). The de-spun antenna in this satellite is a shaped offset reflector which features true hybrid composites construction consisting of polyaramid, chopped graphite, uni-directional graphite laminates and aluminum honeycomb. Once again, graphite-epoxy over machined aluminum core formed the rf reflecting surface. The reflecting surface itself was critical to spacecraft performance since it was designed to provide a shaped beam coverage which, from geosynchronous orbit, closely follows the outline of the main Japanese islands. Reflector construction was specifically designed with the low-expansion characteristics of graphite-epoxy to ensure accuracy of the shaped beam over the operating temperatures of the spacecraft.

Currently at FACC-WDL, construction of the Intelsat V series of global communication satellites is in progress. This three-axis body-stabilized geosynchronous satellite design features extensive use of advanced composites in the main structure, solar array panels, reflectors, feeds and filters. The Intelsat V satellites, the first of which will be launched in 1979, is designed for a capacity of 12000 circuits which is double that of the current Intelsat IVA satellite series while its mass in orbit is only about 25 percent greater. (The Intelsat system of global satellite communications is described in Reference 3). The antenna subsystem consists of graphite-epoxy phased array feeds which operate in the four- and six-gigahertz frequency bands. These make use of dual circular polarizations (right-hand and left-hand) providing utilization of both frequencies in each geographical area (4). Each phased array consists of approximately 80 graphite-epoxy feed elements which are internally metallized with copper. The qualification temperature extremes experienced by the antenna are -180 C and 100 C. These temperature limits are severe especially for resin systems cured at elevated temperatures. In addition, each square graphite-epoxy feed element, due to the use of dual polarization, has to remain square within 0.01° over this temperature range in order to prevent cross-polarization interferences. These requirements necessitate detailed composite material behavior studies under thermal cycling to provide the

designer with an adequate base for electrical, structural and thermal control design.

This paper describes the results of a research and development study on the mechanical and thermal behavior characterization of graphite-epoxy used in microwave applications (5). The major focus is on two areas of practical importance: (a) the effect of long-term thermal cycling on metallized composites, and (b) the stability of the linear coefficient of thermal expansion.

Thermal Cycling of Metallized Graphite-Epoxy Composites

Thermal stresses are developed in both the metal layer and the graphite epoxy substrate during thermal cycling due to differing coefficients of thermal expansion. In this investigation, the effect of long-term thermal cycling of copper clad graphite-epoxy was investigated. An analysis of the thermal stresses induced during temperature cycling was conducted to determine the probable mode of failure. In addition, several specimens were thermally cycled and the failure modes characterized using scanning electron microscopy.

Specimen Configuration and Materials Investigated

The specimen geometry is shown in Fig. 1. Specimens were made using a proprietary technique in which a mandrel is plated with copper, over which graphite-epoxy prepreg is laid up and cured. After curing, during which bonding of the plating to the graphite-epoxy substrate occurs, the mandrel is removed, stripping off the plating which now adheres to the inside of the graphite-epoxy shell. In all cases, the thickness of the electroplated copper layer was maintained at 0.013 mm (0.0005 in.).

Fig. 1. Geometry of copper plated graphite-epoxy specimen

The graphite-epoxy substrates investigated were

- (1) HMS/934 unidirectional tape $(0/\pm 45/90)_S$ lay-up
- (2) HMF 330C/934 woven fabric, $(0/90)_S$ lay-up
- (3) HMF 330C/934 woven fabric with an epoxy intermediate layer between the substrate and the plating, $(0/90)_S$ lay-up
- (4) HMF 196/934 woven fabric (a finer weave than 330C), $(0/90)_S$ lay-up

The resin system was Fiberite Corporation's 934 epoxy system which is a 175 C curing system. HMS is Hercules' high modulus graphite fiber while the graphite fabrics with the HMF designation are woven with Union Carbide's T-300 graphite fiber.

Thermal Fatigue Analysis

An elastoplastic analysis was conducted to determine the stress-strain response of the copper plating on cooling from the cure temperature (171 C) and on cycling between the minimum service temperature (-180 C) and the maximum service temperature (100 C). In the analysis, it is assumed that the coefficients of thermal expansion are independent of temperature and that the two materials (copper and graphite-epoxy) are perfectly bonded to each other. In addition, the graphite-epoxy lay-ups are quasi-isotropic in CTE. For the specimen shape shown in Fig. 1, if the temperature is decreased through $-\Delta T$, and if the corners of the tube are not connected, the plates forming the sides would bow outwards as a result of the higher CTE of the interior plating (Fig. 2a). To re-assemble the box, distributed moments have to be applied along each edge to satisfy the boundary conditions. For a square cross-section, these are equal and opposite.

Fig. 2. Bending moments induced on walls of specimen tube during a negative temperature differential. These distributed moments cancel each other and the square shape of the tube is retained.

From compatibility conditions,

$$\alpha_1 \Delta T + \epsilon_1 = \alpha_2 \Delta T + \epsilon_2 \quad (1)$$

where subscript 1 refers to the copper and 2 to the graphite-epoxy substrate. Modeling the elastoplastic behavior of the copper as a Ramberg-Osgood material (6),

$$\epsilon_1 = \frac{\sigma_1}{E_1} + \frac{3}{7} \frac{\sigma_1}{E_1} \left(\frac{\sigma_1}{\sigma_{.7}} \right)^{n-1} \quad (2)$$

where σ_1 is the uniaxial stress, n the shape factor and $\sigma_{.7}$ the stress at which the secant modulus is $0.7 E_1$. The graphite-epoxy material is modeled as a Hookean material where

$$\epsilon_2 = \frac{\sigma_2}{E_2} \quad (3)$$

From equilibrium,

$$\sigma_1 t_1 = \sigma_2 t_2 \quad (4)$$

where t_1 and t_2 are the thicknesses of the copper and the substrate respectively. Substituting equations (2), (3) and (4) in equation (1), an equation was obtained which, solved numerically, defined the stress state in the plating as a function of the temperature differential. The result of the analysis for the stress-strain state in the copper from cure (when bonding is assumed to occur) to the maximum temperature (100 C) is shown in Fig. 3.

On cooling from the cure temperature, tensile yielding of the copper begins at 125 C (the yield stress of pure annealed copper is 76 MPa). Further cooling to -180 C results in tensile plastic flow in the copper. On raising the temperature, the plating is unloaded along the elastic line BC (Fig. 3). At $T = -134$ C, the stress is zero but there is a net tensile strain of 0.00465. At T greater than -134 C, the stress in the plating becomes compressive. Neglecting the Bauschinger effect, the compressive yielding of the plating begins at -88 C and continues until the maximum temperature of 100 C is reached. On cooling, the material again unloads to zero stress at 54 C along EF and then loads in tension until tensile yield occurs once again but now at 8 C. On thermal cycling between -180 C and 100 C, a hysteresis loop BCDEFG is followed in which the copper layer cycles about a mean strain $\epsilon_m = 0.00322$ with a strain amplitude of $\pm \Delta \epsilon = 0.00208$.

The copper plating, therefore, undergoes low-cycle thermal fatigue. In order to estimate the number of cycles to failure, the following strain-life relationship was used (7):

$$\frac{\Delta \epsilon}{2} = \frac{\sigma_f'}{2} (2N_f)^b + \epsilon_f' (2N_f)^c \quad (5)$$

Fig. 3. Stress-strain history of copper plating from bonding temperature (171 C) to the minimum temperature (-180 C) to the maximum temperature (100 C). Yield strength = 76 MPa.

where σ_f' is the fatigue strength coefficient, ϵ_f' the fatigue ductility coefficient, N_f the number of cycles to failure and b,c constants. Cyclic data on electroplated or electroformed copper was not available; instead, recent data on OFHC copper was used (8):

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_f' &= 621 \text{ MPa} & b &= 0.149 \\ \epsilon_f' &= 0.483 & c &= 0.534 \end{aligned}$$

In Reference 8, the cyclic yield stress was determined to be 138 MPa which is much larger than the monotonic yield stress of 30 MPa indicating that a large amount of work-hardening occurs during cycling. A reasonable assumption is that the electroplated copper (yield stress = 76 MPa) will also cyclically stabilize at a cyclic yield stress of 138 MPa. Using the foregoing values with the strain amplitude determined from the thermal analysis, the predicted number of cycles to failure from equation (5) is

$$N_f = 50000 \text{ cycles}$$

Fig. 4. Schematic cross-section of balanced-weave graphite-epoxy fabric with copper plating.

Thus far, the mechanism of failure considered was one in which the copper plating fails due to low-cycle thermal fatigue. The graphite-epoxy substrate was assumed to be homogeneous and isotropic. In reality, the substrate is non-homogeneous; the structure of a woven fabric substrate is schematically shown in Fig. 4. There are periodic variations in both modulus and the coefficient of thermal expansion adjacent to the plating. As a result of the different coefficients of thermal expansion between 0° and 90° graphite-epoxy tows, thermal stresses are induced in the substrate itself which, during thermal cycling, may cause crack initiation and propagation from the substrate into the plating. For the three material system shown in Fig. 4, the maximum strain amplitude was calculated by the methods described above. For $\Delta T = -351$ C,

$$\Delta \epsilon = 0.011$$

and occurs in the 90° material. For this calculation, the material parameters shown in Table I were used. Recent data on the mechanical fatigue of epoxy (see Fig. 5) show that for strain amplitudes of 0.011, fatigue failure in the 90° tows should occur at (9):

$$N_f = 400 \text{ cycles}$$

The more probable mechanism, therefore, is one in which local thermal fatigue failure, occurring in the 90° zone of the weave, propagates into the plating at a substantially lower number of cycles than would be indicated by considering fatigue failure of the plating alone.

It should be noted that the foregoing calculations have been based on room temperature mechanical property data. In a more accurate analysis,

Table I. Material parameters used in calculating the thermal cyclic strain amplitude in copper-plated woven graphite-epoxy.

Property	0° Graphite-epoxy	90° Graphite-epoxy	Copper
Young's Modulus,	141 GPa (20.5 X 10 ⁶ psi)	7 GPa (1.0 X 10 ⁶ psi)	114 GPa (16.5 X 10 ⁶ psi)
Coefficient of Thermal Expansion,	-0.7 X 10 ⁻⁶ K ⁻¹ (-0.4 X 10 ⁻⁶ F ⁻¹)	32 X 10 ⁻⁶ K ⁻¹ (18 X 10 ⁻⁶ F ⁻¹)	16.5 X 10 ⁻⁶ K ⁻¹ (9.2 X 10 ⁻⁶ F ⁻¹)
Thickness, t	0.13 mm (0.005 in)	0.13 mm (0.005 in)	0.013 mm (0.0005 in)

Fig. 5. Cyclic strain amplitude vs log stress reversals for epoxy, glass fiber and graphite fiber composites (9).

material data as a function of temperature should be incorporated. For example, the coefficient of thermal expansion of copper is not a constant but decreases monotonically towards zero as the temperature approaches absolute zero (10). Thus, use of low temperature data when calculating the stresses at the low temperature extreme (where they are a maximum) will result in a smaller value of the thermal stresses than those obtained using constant room temperature properties. However, the analysis is useful in determining the relative strain magnitudes in these materials and provides a basis for the experimental evaluation described below.

Experimental Determination of Failure Modes

To evaluate experimentally the effect of thermal cycling, the four candidate materials were thermally cycled in a thermal cycling chamber. Each specimen configuration was the same as shown in Fig. 1 and consisted of a rectangular graphite-epoxy tube of 0.25 mm wall thickness with 0.013 mm of electrodeposited copper on the inside surfaces. Temperature cycling was performed in the gas-driven system shown in Fig. 6. This convective heat-transfer system was designed to provide data in a shorter period of time than the thermal vacuum system conventionally used. Dry nitrogen gas was circulated through the chamber to minimize moisture effects. The average cycling rate was about 4 cycles per hour (-180 C to 100 C). Individual specimen tubes were thermocoupled and their temperatures recorded on a strip chart recorder. A thermocouple attached to a centrally placed specimen provided feedback to the controller. The maximum rate of change of temperature was 50 C/min. Because the tubes were oriented in the chamber with their axes parallel to the gas flow and because of their low thermal mass (0.27 mm total wall thickness), the through-thickness thermal gradients were estimated to be small.

Fig. 6. Thermal cycling system.

At 5, 10, 50, 100, 500 and 1000 cycles, 1 cm square specimens were cut from tubes and inspected in an optical microscope. Selected samples were mounted in a scanning electron microscope and the metal surface examined for cracks. A few specimens were mounted perpendicular to the surface and the polished cross-section viewed on an optical microscope. Vacuum-deposited aluminum was applied to improve contrast in the graphite layer.

Fig. 7. Failure occurring in depression formed in plating following 1000 thermal cycles. Substrate was HMF 330 C/934 woven graphite-epoxy, 150 X.

Fig. 8. Magnification of crack tip zone in Fig. 7, 1500 X.

Results

Woven graphite-epoxy substrates. In the woven materials, changes in the metallized surface morphology were noted immediately following the first five thermal cycles. These changes were primarily surface depressions which became progressively more well-defined as cycling proceeded. The depressions were found to be periodic in nature and correlated with the locations of the interstices of the weave. These resin rich areas (and, in some cases, voids) appear to have caused local "sink" marks which were imprinted onto the copper surface after cycling. It should be noted that following cure (according to Fig. 3), the copper plating elongates plastically in tension. On subsequent thermal cycling, the plated layer undergoes a compressive stress which will cause it to buckle into the depressed zone of the woven substrate. This is believed to be the mechanism for the changes noted. In the stress analysis, the assumption was that the plating was well bonded to the substrate and would accept in-plane compression loading.

No cracks were observed in the plating until 500-1000 cycles had elapsed. The cracks observed in this cyclic range were almost always associated with the sink marks noted earlier. Fig. 7 shows a typical failure zone in the center of a depression in the plating following 1000 thermal cycles. Fig. 8 is a higher-magnification micrograph of the tip of the crack in Fig. 7. One sees bifurcation of the main crack and the existence of additional smaller cracks.

Effect of an interface layer. An epoxy interface layer was applied between the graphite-epoxy fabric and the copper plating in order to isolate the inhomogeneities of the weave from the metal layer. Once again, on cycling, little damage was noticed until about 500-1000 cycles had elapsed. The major mode of damage initiation was buckling of the upper layer. Fig. 9 shows a buckled surface which also contains a crack. Since buckling was not noticed in the samples without the interface layer, it was assumed that the interface predisposes the metal layer to fail in this mode. The conjecture is that the lower modulus interface layer does not support the copper rigidly enough during the in-plane compressive stress that the copper experiences during thermal cycling. The situation is analagous to the beam-on-an-elastic-foundation problem where, under compression, the beam (in this case, the copper plating) undergoes a higher-order buckling mode whose order is a function of the modulus of the foundation (the interface layer). Increasing

Fig. 9. Buckling and failure of plating over epoxy interface layer, 150 X.

Fig. 10. Cracks in plating on unidirectional laminated graphite-epoxy (HMS/934) substrate, 150 X.

the modulus of the foundation increases the critical load at which buckling is initiated. Thus the lower-modulus epoxy interface will result in buckling occurring at lower compressive stress levels.

Laminated, unidirectional graphite-epoxy substrates. Unlike the woven substrates, cracks were noticed in these materials at an earlier stage, between 100 and 500 cycles. The cracks were long and extensive and followed the fiber direction of the graphite-epoxy layer immediately adjacent to the plating. Fig. 10 shows a typical surface. A polished cross-section through one such crack revealed that the crack originated from a crack lying in the 1-3 plane in the adjacent graphite-epoxy ply. Similar failures were noted by Camahort, et. al. who subjected graphite-epoxy laminates to 25 thermal cycles between -196 C and 100 C and observed the cross-sections micrographically (11).

The cracks observed in the unidirectional composites were much longer than those observed in the woven materials. It appears that the weave acts

Fig. 11. Schematic of thermal expansion measuring equipment.

as a crack stopper and prevents cracks from propagating more than the length of one overlap. Thus, woven graphite-epoxy is more suitable than laminated unidirectional graphite-epoxy as a substrate material under these thermal cycling conditions.

Stability of the Thermal Expansion Coefficient of Graphite-Epoxy Composites

For the designer of low-expansion composite structures, it is essential that the stability of the coefficient of thermal expansion be characterized over the operating temperature range and life of the spacecraft. The concern is that unaccounted variations in CTE during in-orbit operating may result in failure of the communications system which depends upon the geometrical accuracy of the microwave components for satisfactory operation. A preliminary study was conducted to evaluate changes in the CTE of graphite-epoxy laminates during thermal cycling.

Experimental Technique and Results

The telemicroscope technique was used to determine the CTE of graphite-epoxy tubes fabricated in this program. Fig. 11 shows the experimental set-up. Measurements were made in vacuum (10 torr) using two 50 X telemicroscopes having a least count of 0.5 micrometer (12). The thermal chamber surrounded the specimen completely except for windows through which the measurements were taken. To improve accuracy, a NBS fused silica standard was used and the displacement relative to the standard was measured as shown in Fig. 12. This was also found to be a more reliable technique.

Fig. 12. CTE measurement relative to fused silica standard (12).

Fig. 13. Expansivity data of graphite-epoxy tubular sample.

Readings were taken after the specimens were outgassed for 4 hours at 120 C under vacuum in order to remove most of the moisture and other volatiles in the sample. Temperature cycling was done with the sample in the chamber and measurements of the CTE made after every ten cycles.

Fig. 13 shows some preliminary results measured on a graphite-epoxy tube made with GY-70 (Celanese Corporation) and HMS (Hercules) fibers and 934 epoxy system (Fiberite Corporation). After the initial series of measurements, significant changes in the CTE occur at 11 and 20 thermal cycles from -160 C to 120 C. The low temperature CTE changes sign from negative to positive while the positive high temperature CTE decreases in magnitude. This behavior is unlike that reported by other investigators (see, for example, Reference 11) who show microcracking induced during thermal cycling resulting in a smaller contribution to the CTE from the off-axis plies. Therefore, the CTE, as shown by these investigators, almost always decreases with thermal cycling and approaches that of the unidirectional graphite-epoxy.

The behavior noted in this investigation, in which the CTE may increase with thermal cycling, is most likely due to viscoelastic stress relaxation mechanisms as well as the growth of microdefects between the plies of the tubular specimen. Using ultrasonic reflection techniques, it may be possible to correlate the growth of these defects with the change in the CTE (12).

Conclusions

Characterization of the thermal and mechanical behavior of advanced composites is important in order to provide the designer of communications

spacecraft with an adequate base for electrical, structural and thermal design. For microwave applications, long-term composite materials characterization is especially important since even small local structural displacements due to creep or microcracking may result in failure of the communications system. Two areas of major interest were investigated: the effect of long-term thermal cycling on metallized composites, and the stability of the coefficient of thermal expansion.

An elasto-plastic stress analysis was conducted to determine the stress-strain state of copper plating on various graphite-epoxy substrate materials during thermal cycling. The results show that the plating undergoes elasto-plastic cyclic loading in both the tension and compression regimes. Using low-cycle fatigue theory and recent fatigue data on copper, the number of cycles for low-cycle fatigue failure of the plating was determined. A lower value for the number of cycles-to-failure was also determined when a similar analysis was conducted to determine the stress state of the woven graphite-epoxy substrate using low-cycle mechanical fatigue data on epoxy. The probable failure mechanism predicted by the analysis is one in which microcracks generated by thermal fatigue of the graphite-epoxy substrate propagate into and cause failure of the plating. This finding was essentially corroborated by the results of experimental thermal cycling tests also conducted in this investigation.

Copper plated graphite-epoxy specimens were thermally cycled in a dry nitrogen gas thermal cycling chamber. The metal surface was inspected for microcracks using scanning electron microscopy. For the woven graphite-epoxy substrate materials, cracks in the plating nucleated at regions adjacent to the interstices of the weave. Unlike the laminates made from unidirectional graphite-epoxy, plating cracks in the woven substrates were localized and did not extend beyond an overlap of the weave. It appears that the weave has a crack arresting quality which makes it an attractive candidate for metallized applications.

The predominant failure mode as a result of thermal cycling was one in which microcracks from the graphite-epoxy substrate propagated into the plating. This was verified by cross-sectional micrographs which showed cracks originating in the graphite-epoxy layer adjacent to the plating. The effect of an epoxy interface layer between the plating and the composite was also investigated. Thermal cycling resulted in buckling of the copper plating causing progressive crack initiation and propagation at the surface. This was attributed to the low modulus of the interface which, acting as the foundation to the copper plating under compression, resulted in a lower critical buckling load.

Preliminary data on CTE stability of graphite-epoxy indicated that during initial thermal cycling significant changes in the CTE can occur. These changes, which were measured on tubular specimens, may be attributed to the growth of interlaminar microdefects.

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SESSION 9:
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